

D7.4

LegumES Network Map

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Background to the LegumES project

The legumES project will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumes;
3. that the ES benefits and cost offered by legumes are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, legumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising legumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The legumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multiactor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, 'reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumes use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, LegumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based Pilot Studies which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumESproject.eu

Executive Summary

The legumES Network Map (Deliverable D7.4) documents the development of two complementary resources: an open-access EU Projects Database Tool, and an interactive visual legumES [Network Map](#). Together, these tools identify, organise, and display EU-funded projects aligned with the legumES' themes of legumes, ecosystem services, agroecology, and sustainable agrifood systems. Drawing on CORDIS hosted project data from FP7, Horizon 2020, and Horizon Europe, these resources provide a structured and searchable overview intended to increase awareness of past and ongoing initiatives, support the identification of project synergies, and help stakeholders build on existing work or identify areas of unmet need. In parallel, this deliverable also includes a Large Language Model (LLM)–based analytical assessment of synergies between LegumES and its sister projects VALERECO and LEGENDARY, ensuring that the mapping work is expanded with a deeper exploration of cross-project alignment and complementary activities.

An EU Projects Database Tool was developed in Excel™ to generate the filtered project dataset necessary for visualisation. This tool applies an iterative sequence of automated Power Query transformations, including keyword-based filtering, exclusion of irrelevant projects, and categorisation according to defined thematic areas. While the tool was used to create a dataset associated with specific legumES related themes; it has been designed in such a way that any user can redefine generate a customised project database tailored to their own thematic focus. The validated LegumES project dataset produced by this tool forms the basis of the second output: the open-access LegumES [Network Map](#) and its associated 'living' Google Sheet database. The Google Sheet hosts the baseline dataset and is structured so that external users can add regional, national, or thematic initiatives not present in the CORDIS Framework Project Databases. This sheet serves as the foundation database used to create the Network Map which is hosted on the Kumu platform. The legumES [Network Map](#) visualises projects and their relationships, enabling users to explore thematic linkages, identify geographically or topically aligned projects, and examine research clusters centred on themes such as legumes, ecosystem services, and sustainable farming.

Beyond mapping the project landscape, this deliverable includes a systematic assessment of synergistic interactions between legumES, VALERECO, and LEGENDARY. Using a Large Language Model (LLM), project metadata—including work package descriptions and deliverable titles—was analysed to identify areas of overlap, complementarity, and unique contribution. The analysis produced a unified ecosystem services (ES) framework, highlighted shared thematic domains, and identified common priorities suitable for coordinated planning and joint activities. It also revealed opportunities for methodological harmonisation, integration of digital tools, and the development of aligned policy and dissemination outputs across the three projects.

Through these combined efforts, the creation of a flexible database tool, the development of a dynamic [Network Map](#), and the application of LLM-based cross-project analysis, Deliverable D7.4 enhances the potential for collaboration within the legume research community. It also demonstrates a clear strategy for designing impactful collaboration between complementary projects, specifically legumES, VALERECO, and LEGENDARY.

1. Introduction and Objective

The EU framework programmes which have been in existence for just over 40 years are a series of programmes centred on facilitating research and innovation (R&I) within Europe. The last three iterations of the framework have invested a total of approx. €226 billion through FP7 (± €50.5 billion from 2007 to 2013), Horizon2020 (± €80 billion from 2014 to 2020), and Horizon Europe (± €95.5 billion from 2021 – 2027) (7th Framework Programme for Research, n.d.; Celebrating 40 Years of Innovation: The Journey of EU Framework Programmes | Data.Europa.Eu, n.d.; Funding Programmes and Open Calls - Research and Innovation, n.d.). Each programme is built on the previous one, with continuous review, and made up of different calls associated with different topics. However, the central objective has evolved into driving R&I to combat socioeconomic and environmental challenges and “building a competitive Europe which will also shape a sustainable future” (Science, Research and Innovation Performance of the EU, 2024, 2024).

Figure 1. Evolution of the European framework programme for R&I (Science, Research and Innovation Performance of the EU, 2024, 2024).

Considering this evolution, the need for investment to combat key challenges, including climate change and loss of biodiversity, has been identified. The Horizon Europe strategy highlights R&I needs to achieve the European ‘Green Deal’ which is one of its three strategic orientations, specifically listing areas such as ecosystem protection and designing fair and environmentally friendly agrifood systems.

In addition, increased emphasis has been placed on collaboration, co-creation, and increasing visibility of research and interventions/innovations to maximise impact.

With this strategic focus in mind, legumES Task 7.3 was conceived with two main – and related - aims in mind. Firstly, to **develop a resource the ‘legumES Network Map’**, which is in fact a **database and mapping tool to visualise legume funded projects**. This aims to serve as a means whereby stakeholders can more easily achieve an accurate overview of the vast array of legume-focused projects funded by the EC. This provides a foundation for historic research overviews, awareness building, as a basis for targeted data-/results-mining activities that improve the use of existing knowledge and interventions – and inform meaningful syntheses, plus identification of concrete and new actions that build upon, and do not simply repeat, past advancements. **The legumES Network Map (D7.4)** was therefore developed to facilitate these interactions and serve as a tool for researchers, the public, and policymakers to analyse and visualise initiatives, both active and closed, working on the themes of sustainable agrifood system development.

In addition, a second activity related under this Task is to **identify how synergistic interactions and knowledge / activity gaps may be identified using activity and output metadata of specific projects** – and here using the active sister projects Valereco, and Legendary – in a model approach. This activity was pursued by the assessment of WP Task Descriptions and Deliverable titles and using LLM (Large Language Models; ChatGPT) to identify areas of overlap, synergy, and knowledge or data gaps to help identify and develop strategic plans for common interaction and syntheses, and also development. The purpose of this effort is also to promote joint activities and outputs such as shared promotion activities (e.g. joint symposiums or joint dissemination materials etc.) to optimise resources, reach wider audiences and maximize the impact of the proposed actions. The collaborations identified will also be used to establish a joint working group and formalise a **Missions Document** to identify and define key joint activities and their implementation plans (respectively) for a suite of agreed strategic priorities that will add value to all the current efforts of the parties involved and increase their impacts and legacy.

These approaches, the Network Mapping facility and the downstream use of LLMs, are complementary and are applied here as an integrated model to draw on multidisciplinary insights and capacities across projects focused on sustainable agrifood system development using legumes. With specific reference to the legumES, Valereco, and Legendary projects, the LLM model explores how legumes can be most effectively researched to support the valorisation of ecosystem services.

2. Database and Network Map development

The legumES Network Map development was an iterative process. It first involved exploring the ways in which project data could be visualised and progressed to create a relevant project database for visualisation. The final stage was building the ‘living’ tool which could serve both the legumES project objectives as well as external stakeholders. The following three sections describe each of the phases.

2.1. Initial map development and validation of visualisation approach using the Kumu platform

The database and Network Map development began with the idea to illustrate connections between EU projects, WPs, and tasks using the relationship mapping tool; Kumu (<https://kumu.io/>). The initial phase involved testing this approach by extracting WPs and task data from two projects (LegumES and COUSIN) and trialling the visualisation. Using Google NotebookLM, the project proposals were extracted into a tabular format and tagged to illustrate connections between different tasks. While this approach was successful in providing a visualisation of project activities as well as certain connections; the text parsing to assign relevant tags to each WP and Task using LLM was frequently inaccurate or too broad. In addition, the output was very granular without delivering the needed overview of related past and present projects with which collaborations, or syntheses, can be made (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Initial Network Maps developed. A: legumES project WP's and tasks. B: COUSIN WP's and tasks. C: the connection between tasks of legumES and COUSIN defined by tags including; Stakeholder Engagement; Participatory farmers, and educational activities. Projects are represented by green diamonds, WPs are represented by yellow triangles, Tasks are represented by blue circles; and Tags are represented by orange hexagons.

Through the process of creating this first visualisation, the approach of using Kumu as a method to visualise the data in a public way was validated. After reviewing the needs, it was decided that the next steps would involve broadening the scope to include a wider range of projects, initially without detailed WP and task-level data. Using CORDIS project summaries, relevant tags would then be identified and visualised within the network to illustrate connected projects and their themes. Projects showing strong alignment with legumES can then be engaged for collaboration.

2.2. EU Project database development: project identification and categorisation using Excel™ Power Queries and keywords

To be able to create the Network Map, a database of projects with relevant information and tags was necessary. The following sections describe the pipeline used to compile this baseline data for import into the Kumu platform. Power Query, a built-in Excel™ tool for data cleaning and transformation, was used to filter the data efficiently, apply repeatable rules, and ensure consistency across updates of the dataset.

The resulting Excel™ file, [legumES Network Map Database 2025](#), serves as the Network Map database and as a tool to create future customised databases. It contains the raw project data, the keywords used for filtering, the Power Query transformations applied, and the final output database imported into Kumu. Users can download the file and adjust keywords or filters to generate outputs tailored to their needs. The tabs referenced in the following sections correspond to those within the Excel™ file, which should be reviewed alongside the report.

2.2.1. Compiling and preparing the raw database: FP7, H2020, and HORIZON Europe

Corresponding Excel™ tabs:

Raw Data_projects combined
Raw Data_organisations

The open access raw data for the FP7, Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe programmes was downloaded through Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects>. The project information contained within the relevant Excel™ for each project was combined into a single table and included the following fields as per the labelling in CORDIS:

id, acronym, status, title, startDate, endDate, totalCost, ecMaxContribution, legalBasis, topics, ecSignatureDate, frameworkProgramme, masterCall, subCall, fundingScheme, objective, contentUpdateDate, rcn, grantDoi, keywords.

The keywords (listed in the 'keywords' column) were reformatted to be separated by pipelines (|) rather than commas as the Kumu platform does not read comma separated items as independent inputs but rather as a string of text. In addition, the values in the 'ecMaximumContributions' column were reformatted so that decimal separators were dots (.) and not commas (,) as it was found that the Excel™ was reading all comma's as thousands separators. This formatting was maintained or added across all the data throughout the process. A separate CORDIS Excel™ containing all the organisation and respective country information affiliated with each 'project id' was also downloaded and

combined for Frameworks FP7, Horizon2020, and Horizon Europe. The combined data was summarised to include only the following fields:

projectID, projectAcronym, organisationID, name, shortName, city, country, organizationURL

2.2.2. First stage filtering and data compilation:

Corresponding Excel™ tabs:	Corresponding Power Queries
<i>Key_filtering 1</i>	<i>Filtered projects based on Key</i>
<i>Projects_filtered 1</i>	<i>Filtered_orgs based on projects</i>
<i>Organisations_filtered 1</i>	<i>Merged Projects&Orgs</i>
<i>Merged_Projects&Orgs_filtered 1</i>	

The combined raw database included all funded projects ranging from topics on agriculture and food systems to history and mobile network architecture with a total of 79,840 projects contained within the raw project database and 435,976 entries in the raw organisations database (note, a single organisation could be listed any number of times depending on how many projects that organisation has been/is part of). For this reason, a first stage filtering was conducted to reduce the database into projects that were more likely to align with the ‘legumes’, ‘ecosystem services’, ‘agroecology’, and ‘sustainable agri-food system’ themes. This was done by using Power Query (*Filtered projects based on Key*) to search for specified keywords (*Key_filtering 1*) within the text of the ‘Objective’ column for each project and return a table of projects (*Projects_filtered 1*). The consequence of this query is that each project in the initial filtered output contains at least one of the specified keywords.

The decision was made to define keywords and search for these within the projects objectives instead of using the keywords from the CORDIS database because not all projects in the raw database had associated keywords. In the cases where keywords were listed, they were often not based on general themes but were rather very project specific. The keywords used for first stage filtering can be found in Table 1 and the Excel™ tab titled: ‘Key_filtering 1’.

Table 1. List of keywords used to filter raw CORDIS data for projects aligning with the LegumES themes of ecosystem services, agroecology and sustainable agrifood systems.

Keywords
Legumes
Ecosystem Services
Nature based solutions
Regenerative agriculture
Agroecology
Agroecological
Cropping
Farmers
Farm
Ecosystem Service
Agriculture
nature-based solutions

To assess whether the keywords were extracting relevant projects, a series of reviews took place. This involved cross-referencing a pre-defined project list against the output table and confirming that each

project could be identified by the keywords. This list (Table 2) was compiled prior to building the Network Map, and was developed by Pietro Iannetta (legumES project Coordinator), and Mr Roger Vickers (legumES Science Steering Board Chairperson) based on existing knowledge regarding EU projects related to the above legumES’ themes. In each case that a project was not ‘identified’ the objective item of the specific project was read and relevant keyword selected for inclusion and re-testing.

Table 2. EU funded projects related to the legumES and other related calls used as a reference list to validate filtering keyword choices for Network Map database compilation.

EU Funded Projects			
EUCLEG	Valpropath	InterCrop	Oper-8
Legumes Translated	Eurolegume	Nodperception	Pathways
Legume Hub	ABstress	PreLeg	Project ô
LegValue	Legato	FITTER	Protein enrichment
DiverImpacts	Legume Gap	Agromix	Remix Intercrops
DiverFarming	Increase	Biodiversity	Smart Chain
Diversify	Legume Futures	Circular Agronomics	Solace
Remix	LEGENDARY	DiverImpacts	Super-G
True project	VALERECO	DIVERSify	TOMRES
Crop Diversification cluster	legumES	Landmark	Unalab
Legume Generation	LIFT project	LegumeGap	TRUE
BELIS	Legume Root Impact	Legumes Translated	ProLEgSo
Intercrop Values	LeguVal	LegValue	Grain Legumes
Leguminose	LegumePlus	Libbio	

The outcome of this initial filtering resulted in a table containing 3,062 projects (*Projects_filtered 1*). These project IDs were then used to perform a second query (*Filtered_orgs based on projects*) in which the raw database of organisations and countries was reduced to only contain the data linked to the filtered project output (*Organisations_filtered 1*). These two queries were then merged (*Merged Projects&Orgs*) and labels refined to produce an output containing the fields found in Table 3 (output tab: *Merged_Projects&Orgs_filtered 1*).

Table 3. Power Query output fields after first stage data filtering and merging.

Field (database table heading)	Description of field
Label	This is equivalent to the project acronym and was relabelled to Label for the Kumu platform field identification needs.
Type	This describes the framework programme (fp7, H2020, Horizon).
Project Keywords	This field contains the CORDIS listed keywords per project.
Description	The CORDIS objectives field was relabelled ‘Description’ to align with Kumu platform field identification needs.
Project title	The project title
id	The CORDIS project ID.
Start Data	Start Date.

Field (database table heading)	Description of field
End Date	End Date
Maximum contributions (euros)	The maximum contributions to the project rounded to remove the decimal place which was being considered a thousand separator in Power Query.
Topics	Topics.
Master Call	Master Call.
Sub Call	Sub Call.
Funding Schemes	Funding Schemes.
Type (for Kumu map classification)	Kumu uses 'Types' to distinguish between different types of data. The type given to this entire dataset was Research Project (EU Funded)
General keywords	This field contains the keywords from Table 1 used to filter in the data.
Participating institutions (full name)	This field contains all the participating institutions affiliated with each project.
Participating institutions (abbr.)	As above.
City	This field contains all the cities of the participating institutions affiliated with each project.
Country	This field contains all the countries of the participating institutions affiliated with each project.
Normalised Description	This field contains the normalised description (all lower-case, and no punctuation. This was used for the second stage of filtering and categorisation).

2.2.3. Second stage filtering and categorisation

Corresponding Excel™ tabs:	Corresponding Power Queries
<i>Tags</i>	<i>Categorised final output</i>
<i>Categorised Projects</i>	

Through random selection of projects and evaluation of their descriptions (labelled objectives in CORDIS and relabelled for Kumu), it became clear that while filtering included reference list (Table 2) and related projects, there was high inclusion of projects that do not align with the target themes. For example, many aquaculture, wind farm, and history related projects were filtered in. While many of these related to the themes of farming, nature-based solutions etc., they were a step removed from the target for the Network Map. For this reason, and to build in project categorisation to visualise connections between projects, a final query was created to exclude projects containing certain keywords, and categorise projects based on other keywords (*Tags*). The exclusion keywords used were chosen by parsing through project descriptions and can be found in (Table 4) and the Excel™ tab titled: 'Tags'.

Table 4. Keywords used to exclude projects from the final filtered and categorised data

Keywords to exclude from the filtered data
History
Wind
Aquaculture
Insects
Marine
History
Superconducting
Algae
Seafood
Filmmaking
Batteries
Seaweed
Archaeology
Aquatic

The categorisation of projects served to give projects ‘Tags’ which would then be used in the Network Map to give an overview of a project’s ‘scope’. Therefore, an insight into more than just the research area, with added ‘how’/ ‘what’ behind the project aim. In other words, the categories (later ‘Tags’) indicate both the project's theme (what it focuses on e.g., legumes) and/or its approach or target output (e.g., multi-actor engagement or material development). To develop generalisable categories and obtain an initial guiding keyword list, approximately 15 project objectives were copied into ChatGPT. The LLM was then prompted to output a suggested list based on these objectives. The final Power Query (*Categorised final output*) was then designed to run a search function, comparing the normalised (lowercase, punctuation-free) project descriptions against the exclusion and categorisation keywords. This was done on the pre-filtered data output from the first stage (Section 2.2.2). Any projects containing excluded keywords were removed from the final output while any projects containing categorising keywords were ‘tagged’ with the corresponding category. The Power Query was designed so that projects could be assigned more than one category. For example, if the legumES project description contains both the words ‘legumes’, and ‘Ecosystem Services’ it would be ‘tagged’ with the categories of; ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’, and ‘Ecosystem Services & Environmental Benefits’.

Similar to the first stage filtering, the exclusion and categorising keywords were then iteratively edited based on random assessment of category allocation and project description in the final output table. The output was also assessed to confirm that all reference projects (Table 2) were retained and categorised reasonably. The final categories and associated keywords can be found in Table 5 and the Excel™ tab titled: Tags.

Table 5. Keywords used to filter and categorise EU funded projects according to themes. The category (theme) titles have been used as ‘Tags’ for the visualisation of connections between different projects in the final Network Map.

Category (labelled Tag in the final output)	Keywords
Agrobiodiversity & Genetic Resources	Underutilised crops, landraces, breeding diversity, crop diversity, livestock farming, breeding, genetic resources
Legumes & Protein Crops	legume, legumes, lupin, faba bean, chickpea, lentil, protein crop, grain legume, legume integration
Ecosystem Services & Environmental Benefits	ecosystem service, ecosystem services, ES benefit, ES cost, nature-based solutions, nature-based solutions, water quality, soil quality, biodiversity
Agroecology & Sustainable Farming	Intercropping, crop rotation, sustainable agriculture, regenerative, cropping system, mixed cropping, intercropping, conservation agriculture, cropping, Integrated pest management, Agricultural sector, sustainable farming, farm sustainability
Value Chains & Market Systems	Farming system, agri-food chain, food system, socioeconomic, agri-food systems, smart farming, common agricultural policy, farm-to-farm, farm to fork, Agriculture network, agriculture networks, agri-food markets, agricultural business models, agricultural value chain, Value chain
Food; Nutrition & Health	recipe, food quality, sustainable food, food producers, diet health, dietary choice, food products, novel food
Soil and Land Management	soil health, cultivation practices, cultivation, cropping, marginal lands
Co-learning & Multi-actor Engagement	multi-actor, multi-actor, multi actor, codesign, co-design, participatory, capacity building, living labs, living-lab
Consumer & Citizen engagement	Citizen science, co-creation, consumer awareness, consumer preference, consumer preferences
Policy; Governance & Regulation	policy recommendations, policy toolkit, policy analysis, CAP alignment, governance models, transition pathways, scenario modelling, regulation / standards, policy stakeholder engagement
Knowledge Exchange & Material Development	Decision Support Tool, Farmer Toolkit, Manual / Handbook, Best Practice Guidelines, Digital App, Dashboard, Modelling Tool, Training Materials, Policy Toolkit
Digital Tools; Modelling & Sustainability Assessment	digital platform, AI/ML, simulation model, LCA ¹ , ES modelling, scenario modelling, predictive analytics

The outcome of this second stage filtering and categorisation resulted in a table containing **1,665 projects** and their associated tags, institutions, and countries which could then be used to begin building the [Network Map](#) in Kumu and will be referred to as the [‘legumES EU Projects Master database’](#) (*Categorised Projects*). The projects, based as far as possible on the text in their descriptions (originally labelled ‘Objectives’ in the CORDIS database), are EU-funded and relate to one or more general themes, including agroecology, legumes, ecosystem services, and sustainable agrifood systems.

¹ LCA (Life Cycle Assessment)

For import into Kumu, a few specific fields are required such as ‘Label’, ‘Type’, ‘Tag’, and ‘Description’. The project ‘Type’ was initially defined as the Framework Programme, however this was later changed to rather describe the type of entry; for example, whether the entry was describing an EU or regionally funded research project, thematic network/cluster, or working group/task force. This was done to facilitate the creation of a ‘living’ [Network Map](#) to which external users can add data and create more opportunity for cross-network synthesis, or for live projects - collaboration. This will be explained further in section 2.3 but the simple consequence is that the ‘Type’ field was changed to reflect the project types as ‘Research Project (EU Funded)’. After some other minor heading adjustments, the final database was complete and contains the fields found in Table 6 (output tab: *Categorised Projects*).

Table 6. Final Power Query output fields in the complete database after second stage filtering and categorisation. Database titled; legumES EU Projects_Master.

Field (database table heading)	Description of field
Label	This is equivalent to the project acronym and was relabelled to Label for Kumu platform field identification needs.
Type	This describes the type of data entry. The type given to this entire dataset was Research Project (EU Funded).
Tags	The tags refer to the category assigned after keyword-description searching.
Description	The CORDIS ‘objectives’ field was relabelled ‘Description’ to align with Kumu field identification needs.
Project Keywords	This field contains the CORDIS listed keywords per project.
Project title	The project title.
id	The CORDIS project ID
Funding Programme	The CORDIS ‘Framework Programme’ was relabelled ‘Funding Programme’ to allow for data entry for projects or initiatives not funded by EU Framework Programmes.
Start Data	Start Date.
End Date	End Date.
Maximum contributions (euros)	The maximum contributions to the project rounded to remove the decimal place which was being considered a thousand separator in Power Query.
Topics	Topics.
Master Call	Master Call.
Sub Call	Sub Call.
Funding Schemes	Funding Schemes
General keywords	This field contains the keywords from Table 1 used to filter in the data
Participating institutions (full name)	This field contains all the participating institutions affiliated with each project.
Participating institutions (abbr.)	As above.
City	This field contains all the cities of the participating institutions affiliated with each project.
Country	This field contains all the countries of the participating institutions affiliated with each project.

Field (database table heading)	Description of field
Tag keywords	This field contains the keywords that were identified within the description resulting in the specific categorisation/tagging.

2.3. LegumES Network Map: developing an open-access network map and 'living' database using the Kumu platform

Through the Excel™ Power Query pipeline, a refined database was developed which could be imported into the Kumu platform to create the legumES Network Map. Kumu facilitates Excel™ file import as well as linkage to a Google Sheet with the only criteria being to label the first four fields with Kumu recognisable text. As has been described in section 0, these fields are 'Label', 'Type', 'Tags', and 'Description'. The following sections describe the process of structuring the Network Map as well as the development of the google sheet ultimately being used for continuous update of the map.

The complete legumES Network Map and its underlying Google Sheet database can be accessed at the links below and should be viewed alongside the following sections:

- [legumES Network Map Database \(google sheet\)](#)
- [legumES Network Map](#)

2.3.1. Structuring the legumES Network Map

Kumu allows any viewer of a public map to make (impermanent) changes to how the data is presented and view elements or connections of interest. However, Kumu also has the functionality for the map owner(s) to create map views that users can use to help guide exploration of the data. Therefore, the initial map development stage involved exploring how to create different map views and visualise the data in such a way that users would be able to explore projects meaningfully. For example:

- viewing projects relevant to their field (e.g. legumES visualising legume related projects);
- viewing projects available for collaboration in specific regions;
- understanding project scope; and,
- visualising active and closed projects.

After initial experimentation with the addition of map filters, using tags as connections, and general use of the embedded Kumu editor functionality, a series of map views was created (presented in Section 3). However, through the process it became evident that there was potential for increased impact by making the input database dynamic rather than static.

2.3.2. The legumES Network Map and Database: a dynamic Open-Access tool

The [legumES EU Projects Master database](#) is a collection of EU funded projects related to the legumES funding call or similar present/past calls. Therefore, the database does not showcase projects or initiatives that are funded by different funding bodies or Networks/Working groups etc. This can be considered a 'blind spot' in the baseline data as knowing about regional or international initiatives with similar scopes is beneficial both to legumES as well as possible other map users to investigate

possible collaborations. As Kumu has the functionality to connect with a **Google Sheet**², the decision was made to transfer the [legumES EU Projects Master database](#) to a Google Sheet which external users could add their own information to. Continuous use of this Google Sheet has potential to result in a rich database of varied projects and initiatives related to the overarching themes, accessible to anyone.

The structure of the table to which users can add information was matched to [legumES EU Projects Master database](#). Where applicable (Type, Tags, and Country) drop-down lists were created for users to select inputs which align with the ‘...Master’ data. The ‘Type’ field options include: ‘Research Project (EU Funded)’, ‘Research Project (Regionally Funded)’, ‘Thematic Network/Cluster’, and ‘Working Group/Task Force’. The decision to facilitate the addition of different types of projects and initiatives is what informed the ‘Type’ change away from ‘Framework Programme’ as was mentioned in Section 0 Table 6. The Tagging options given in the drop-down match the tags in Table 5, and the full table of categories and associated keywords was included in a ‘Key’ tab of the Google Sheet to guide users on tagging decisions if necessary. Instructions were added to the Google Sheet and included explanation of what the [Network Map](#) is, how to add data, and how the [legumES EU Projects Master database](#) was developed.

For live import of the data into Kumu, a new tab was created in which a function was added to actively merge the [legumES EU Projects Master database](#) with the user added data (tab: Project/working group additions). This tab titled **Combined data_KUMU** is the complete ‘living database’ and has been linked to the Kumu LegumES [Network Map](#) (all other sheets have ‘ignore’ added to the title so that Kumu does not read that data).

After reimporting the database, the different views of the legumES [Network Map](#) were created and made live. A brief user-guide was added to the map overview to support interpretation and manipulation of the different views. A high-level description of each view can be found in section 3.

3. Key Results

3.1. Description and Functionality of LegumES Network Map views

With the different tools developed, the following section introduces the map views that were created to support user interaction with the data, and to demonstrate the various ways in which the data can be examined. In the context of this map, ‘*elements*’ refer to the individual nodes, each representing a single project or initiative within the legumES database.

Different controls have been added to the views to give users options on how to filter and view the data while also illustrating what could be done to create a custom view if desired. Across all views, a set of standard **filters** has been added to allow users to explore the map according to a range of project characteristics. The filters are elaborated below.

- **Country:** allows users to select one or more countries to display only the projects associated with those locations. In line with the CORDIS database, only country codes are used. A lookup

² A **Google Sheet** is a free, cloud-based spreadsheet you can create and edit in your web browser. It works like Microsoft Excel™ but is stored online in Google Drive and runs entirely via a web browser. Collaboration/edits with others can occur in real time - and it easily connects with other Google apps such as Google Forms and Docs.

table in the [Google Sheet](#)'s 'Key' tab lists all codes and their corresponding countries. The list follows ISO 3166 country codes, except for Greece, which is represented as EL.

- **Type (Research Project / Network / etc.):** refers to the 'Type' field which has been explained in section 2 and which categorises each data entry based on what kind of project or initiative it is. Four options have been created: 'Research Project (EU Funded)', 'Research Project (Regionally Funded)', 'Thematic Network / Cluster', 'Working Group / Task Force'.
- **Tags (thematic category):** includes the categories assigned to each project to give a snapshot of its scope (Table 5). They indicate both the project's theme (what it focuses on, e.g., legumes) and/or its approach or target output (e.g. multi-actor engagement or material development).
- **Funding Programme:** lists the different funding programmes under which projects may be supported. The initial dataset includes the Framework Programmes: FP7, Horizon 2020, and Horizon Europe. As users add data, this list may expand to include regional schemes and other EU or non-EU funding sources.
- **Status (active / closed):** allows users to display only projects that are either active or closed. Project status is continuously updated based on the "Today's Date" function in the feeder [Google Sheet](#), ensuring the map reflects real-time project status.
- **Participating Institution (abbr.):** allows users to identify projects in which specific institutions are involved. Users can select multiple institutional abbreviations to display the projects in which those institutions participate. For example, if a user wants to see all projects in which UCP, and/or JHI are involved; the abbreviations for these institutions can be selected. A reference table in the [Google Sheet](#)'s 'Key' tab lists all abbreviations and their corresponding institutions, following the format used in the CORDIS database.

3.2. View 1: Legume Projects

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 1. Legume Projects • Kumu](#)

The first map view illustrated in Figure 3 shows all projects tagged with the thematic category 'Legumes & Protein Crops'. Using Kumu's advanced editor, elements (the project nodes) have been colour-coded based on their associated tags. Small coloured 'flags' attached to each element give a visual summary of all additional tags linked to each project. The legend in the bottom left indicates which tag is linked to which colour³.

The filter buttons above the map allow users to highlight or hide projects based on associated tags, while the filter buttons at the bottom of the map allow users to filter projects based on the funding source. These can be used together with the filtering tools in the bottom-right corner to further narrow down the dataset.

³ User note: To colour the elements based on 'Tags' the 'paired' colour pallet is necessary. This is because the other colour pallets do not have enough colours for the number of tags.

Figure 3. LegumES Network Map View 1: Legume Projects.

3.3. View 2: Legumes and Ecosystem Service Projects

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 2. Legumes & Ecosystem Services Projects • Kumu](#)

The second view shows all projects that have been tagged with ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’ or ‘Ecosystem Services and Environmental Benefits’. Similarly to the first map view, the elements have been assigned coloured ‘flags’ based on their associated tags, and filtering buttons have been added to the top of the map based on tags as well. The button at the bottom of the map labelled ‘Tags’ allows users to connect projects based on their associated categories. The two buttons beneath this then allow users to showcase which projects in the map are active or closed.

The starting view and the views after connecting and showcasing are presented in Figure 4A. What Figure 4B (after applying connections) illustrates is how projects are clustered based on the similarity between their tags. All projects that have only been tagged with ‘Ecosystem Services and Environmental Benefits’ (red flag) are clustered to the right, while projects with only the ‘Legume & Protein Crops’ tag (purple) are clustered to the left. Projects in the centre have more overlapping additional tags. This view helps illustrate which projects have strong alignment regarding scope (based on the high-level tagging done in section 2) and, using the showcase feature (Figure 4C), can help identify projects with which collaborations can be co-ordinated.

A

B

C

Figure 4. A series of views from legumES Network Map View 2: Legumes and Ecosystem Services Projects. A: starting map view of all ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’ and ‘Ecosystem Services and Environmental Benefits’ tagged projects. B: All projects from A, connected by associated tags. C: All active projects clustered based on connections.

3.4. View 3: Legumes and Ecosystem Service Projects: split

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 3. Legumes & Ecosystem Services Projects: split • Kumu](#)

This view (Figure 5) shows the same filtered projects as the second view. However, the projects have been split with the inner circle showcasing all the ‘Legume & Protein Crop’ projects and the outer circle containing the rest of the projects. The filter buttons and list of filter options can be used to visualise the different projects and their split based on associated tags. Figure 5B illustrates the Horizon projects that have at least one partner country being Denmark (DK) with the centre circle being the projects that have specifically been tagged with ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’.

Figure 5. A legumes Network Map View 3: Legumes and Ecosystem Service Projects: split. A: all projects split based on whether the projects have been tagged with ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’, those that have remain in the inner circle. B: an illustration of the project ‘split’ for Horizon Europe funded projects with at least on partner country being Denmark (DK).

3.5. View 4: All projects connected by major themes

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 4. All projects connected by major themes • Kumu](#)

The fourth view showcases all projects in the database and their connections based on their tags (Figure 6A). Elements have been coloured according to the associated funding programme and shaped based on the 'Type' field. The filters have been kept at their default position in the top left and can be used to visualise country specific etc. projects. Projects can be found within the view by searching for the name (this can be done in all the map views using the search bar) (Figure 6B) This view serves as a baseline from which more detailed perspectives can be generated. By right-clicking on any element and selecting 'Focus', users can display only the connections radiating out from that element (Figure 6C). Up to three levels of focus can be applied (Figure 6D). For projects with many associated tags there might not be a big visual change. However, focusing from a tag element (for example, 'Soil and Land Management') using indirect focus (e.g., two levels out) provides a clearer thematic picture. This highlights both the projects directly linked to the selected tag and the additional tags connected through those projects, making the thematic relationships more interpretable and clustering projects that are more closely connected (Figure 6E).

A

B

C

D

E

Figure 6. legumES Network Map View 4: All projects connected by major themes. A: the starting view of all projects with central nodes (elements) being the ‘Tags’. B: an illustration of how to search for a specific project within the Network Map. C and D: a focussed view which can be done by right clicking on an element; and E: an indirect focussed view of projects and tags associated with the central category of ‘Soil and Land Management’.

3.6. View 5: Legume projects showcased in the entire network

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 5. Legume projects showcased in the entire network • Kumu](#)

The fifth view is a duplication of the fourth with the additional element being that legume projects have been showcased to illustrate where they lie within the network (Figure 7A). Once again, elements have been assigned coloured flags based on associated tags to further visualise project clustering. Buttons have been added to the bottom of the map to allow project filtering based on funding programme and/or their status (active/closed) (Figure 7B).

Figure 7. legumES Network Map View 5: Legume projects showcased in the entire network. A: All legume tagged projects showcased within the network; and B: active legume tagged projects.

3.7. View 6: Legume projects coloured by funding programme

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 6. Legume projects coloured by funding programme • Kumu](#)

Similarly to the first map, the sixth map view presents all ‘Legume & Protein Crop’ tagged projects. In this view, elements have been coloured based on the associated funding programme (Figure 8).

Figure 8. legumES Network Map View 6: Legume projects coloured by funding programme

3.8. View 7: Portugal projects only: illustration of Kumu filtering outcome

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 7. Portugal projects only: illustration of kumu filtering outcome • Kumu](#)

The seventh view was created to illustrate how projects could be filtered based on associated countries, in this case Portugal (Figure 9A). The base view is all projects in which Portugal is one of the participating countries. The 'Tags' button at the bottom of the map can be used to cluster the projects based on their associated tags (Figure 9B). As with the other views, the funding programme buttons can be used to filter down the elements and the 'Active'/'Closed' buttons used to showcase certain projects.

A

B

Figure 9. legumES Network Map View 7: Portugal projects only: illustration of Kumu filtering outcome. A: all projects with Portugal as one of the participating countries. B: projects clustered based on associated tags.

3.9. View 8: Portugal projects only: illustration of Kumu filtering outcome

Link to the specific map view: [legumES Network Map • LegumES network map / 8. Full map no filter • Kumu](#)

The final view prepared (Figure 10) shows all the projects in the database without any underlying filtering or connection. The only visualisation applied is colouring elements based on the associated Funding Programme. Filtering, showcasing and connecting buttons have all been added to the map to give users the opportunity to create a custom view from the full database if desired. The standard list of fields for filtering has been placed at the bottom right along with the search bar and 'Active'/'Closed' showcasing buttons. The 'Tag' button as in the other views allows projects to be connected based on tags and is above the filtering buttons for associated funding programme. The list of buttons above the map are all the tags which can be used to filter down the projects as well. Users are also able to edit the map and controls by using the settings panel as has been depicted in Figure 14 and described in section 4.2.

Figure 10. LegumES Network Map View 8: Full map no filter.

3.10. High level exploration of the landscape developed through the Network

Map process

As presented in the introduction, approximately €226 billion has been committed to project funding across the FP7, H2020, and Horizon Europe Framework Programmes. Of the 79,840 projects funded to date, 1,665 projects (21%) were filtered into the final database centred on showcasing legume, ecosystem service, sustainable food system, and/or agroecology centred projects. These projects have been awarded a collective €5,930,952,449 (€5.9 billion) across all three Framework Programmes assessed (approx. 3% of all projects funded), with 81 of the projects being connected in some way to legumes and receiving a total of €236,114,861 funding. To have greater impact on the challenges that these projects aim to address; increased investment is needed into this sector and more emphasis placed on building off work done.

Through the legumES Network Map, 26 active legume linked projects have been identified with 11 also being tagged with the theme of ‘Ecosystem Services & Environmental Benefit’. These projects serve as a starting point for exploring collaborations and building networks (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Illustrates current active projects with the tag ‘Legumes & Protein Crops’.

4. Closing Comments: utility of the EU Project Database Tool and legumES Network Map

The process from database development to network map construction has resulted in a set of dynamic and visual tools that can be used by all interested stakeholders either to create their own EU Project databases or contribute to and interact with the online legumES database and map. While the tools were developed to create a legumES Network Map, they do not only serve the legumES project but can be used by anyone else willing to mine and visualise EU project data. The following sections describe how to use them, as well as detailing the limitation and functional considerations to keep in mind during editing.

4.1. Utility of the EU Projects Database Tool

In developing the project database, Excel™ was used to leverage existing software expertise. While this approach effectively delivered the required dataset for the Kumu visualisation, future iterations would benefit from using more specific programming language-based tools to enhance the efficiency of the process. However, in developing the filtering pipeline to achieve the objective, the tool emerged as something accessible to a wide audience.

4.1.1. Using and updating the EU Projects Database Tool

- **Who can use the tool?** The pipeline to filter and categorise EU Projects for use in the Network Map was built in Excel™ which is a relatively accessible and user-friendly software programme. Any Microsoft Excel™ user can download the file and manipulate the filtering words (first

keywords, exclusion keywords, categorisation tags etc.) to suit any topic and create a custom database. A 'READ ME' tab has also been added to the tool to guide users.

- **How can the database be updated or different data filtering be applied?**
 - New bulk data can be added to the 'raw' project and organisation sheets to increase the number of projects evaluated for filtering. The existing data can also be completely replaced with different data. However, the headings would need to be kept the same.
 - If adding new data, it is important to remember to go to the specific columns in which there is comma separated information and replace all the commas with pipelines. In addition, all decimal points should be converted to dots, not commas as the Excel reads commas as thousand separators.
 - Keywords can be changed within any of the keyword tables.
 - Any keyword changes or updating of the raw data will require a query refresh. This will then execute the data transformation without any need for further interaction from the user.
- **How can Power Queries be refreshed to reflect changes?** Certain queries would need to be refreshed depending on where the edits take place. For example,
 - **Refresh all:** all Power Queries will need to be refreshed if additional data is added to the 'raw' databases or changes are made to the first-stage filtering keywords (Table 1). This can be done by going to the "Data" tab in the Excel and selecting "Refresh All" (Figure 12 A).
 - **Refresh specific queries:** Only the final queries would need to be refreshed if changes are made to the 'tagging' or 'exclusion' keywords. This can be done by selecting "Queries and Connections" from the Excel™ "Data" tab which will then open a side window showcasing the different Power Queries. The specific Power Query that needs refreshing can then be refreshed (in this case the 'Categorised final output' query) (Figure 12B).
- **How can the Power Query pipeline be reviewed or edited?** To understand the processes happening within the queries and edit any transformation, formula, headings etc. the queries can be edited by right clicking on the query and selecting edit (Figure 12C). Once loaded, the popout window will show all the different steps that have been applied to the Power Query and these steps can be modified or added-to depending on the desired output (Figure 12D). For general database use, this is unlikely to be necessary.

Figure 12. Illustration of where to update and manipulate the database Power Queries to customise the outputs. A: Refreshing all Power Queries after raw data addition or edits. B: Refreshing a specific Power Query to reflect keyword changes in the final output. C and D: Editing/reviewing the Power Query pipeline.

4.1.2. Limitations and points to be aware of when using the tool

- Loading time:** The biggest limitation to using the Excel™ database tool is time and efficiency as any keyword adjustment or reprocessing of the data can take up to 2 hours to load depending on how many queries need rerun. However, the system can run in the background while other tasks are being performed.
- Table headings cannot be changed within standard Excel™ tabs:** an important aspect to understand about the system design, is how data is referenced. Power Queries by default use column headings as fixed labels rather than relying on positional or cell referencing. What this means is that changes to table headings cannot be made within the standard Excel™ tabs but would need to be made within the relevant Power Query and then each subsequent step that refers to the changed heading, because the steps would refer to the original heading and often not automatically update. Therefore, for the raw data tables; data content can be changed, but the existing column headings must remain consistent to avoid breaking the query steps. The recommended best practice for changing the headings in the final output is to add renaming steps within the final Power Query (by editing it) to maintain the integrity of the source data connections.
- The headings and keywords can be changed in the categorisation table (Tags tab):** the default behaviour of using headings as fixed labels has been overridden by the categorisation table (Table 5) to allow users to add new categories and keywords or insert additional columns without editing the queries. Therefore, for any user wishing to make new categories and define keywords that will help sort projects into categories, this can be done in standard Excel™ with no need to open Power Query.

4.1.3. Takeaways regarding using and editing the Excel™ database:

- Contents within the raw data tables can be changed freely, however column headings should not be changed.
- All keywords can be edited freely but column headings for these tables should also not be changed.

- The categorisation table headings and words within the categories can be changed normally within Excel™.
- Changing column headings for the desired output should be done at the final step within the Power Query or manually by copy-pasting the output data into a separate sheet and editing the headings normally.
- Power Queries need to be refreshed for changed in keywords or raw data to be reflected in output tables.

4.1.4. Potential limitations of the keyword filter: reviewing projects within the final legumES EU Projects_Master database

As has now been described, the process to the [legumES EU Projects Master database](#) involved iterative keyword selection and output project evaluation using a reference list. The use of hardcoded keywords means that there is potential for inconsistencies. Specifically, if certain keywords have been overlooked or if project descriptions do not use the specific words, there is potential for relevant projects to be missed during the filtering and categorisation process. Similarly, if certain exclusion keywords were overlooked, there is potential for irrelevant projects to enter the database. With the opportunity to continuously update and refine the keywords used in the pipeline and the Kumu Network Map being a 'live' output. Any errors observed or reported can be corrected.

4.2. Utility of the legumES Network Map and google sheet

The [Network Map](#) and [Google sheet](#) have both been designed to be as user-friendly as possible with instruction and guidelines included in each. One of the major limitations of the map, as with the Excel™ pipeline is time-to-load. Due to the large database, the map can take up to 2 minutes to load which is not something most internet users accept in today's age. However, to manage expectations, a disclaimer has been added to the overview section of the map to 'warn' users that the map might take some time to load.

In terms of developing the deliverable (D7.4) outlined in task 7.3 the [Network Map](#) goes beyond purely visualising legume related projects and serves as a database and resource for users to engage with and manipulate to suite their own interests. Each element within the map can be clicked on to view the details about that Project/Initiative and, in instances where the data is too much to view in the side panel (e.g., country and Institution abbr.) can be accessed through the [Google Sheet](#) (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Side-panel information accessible through the LegumES Network Map.

Different map views have been created to help users initially engage. However, each user can freely apply filters or different edits to the map to visualise specific information. This can be done using the buttons and filters added to the map or working with the options in the settings panel (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Illustration of how the map can be edited using the settings panel.

4.3. Management of the database and Network Map

Throughout legumES project activity, the baseline database will be updated annually by revising the Horizon raw data input to ensure newly funded projects are reflected in Network Map.

The [Google Sheet](#) is Open Access and both the sheet and Network Map will be shared across media channels with a 'Call-to-Action' for project and initiative addition. This will be done at a later stage once the methodology to build the Network Map has been published. The data is stored within a legumES Google Drive and managed by legumES project partners.

5. Developing co-operative plans between projects and initiatives

The legumES Network Map facilitates high level identification of alignment between projects and initiatives. However, the CORDIS database, and therefore the Network Map, does not include detail on WP/Task/deliverable breakdown for each project. What this means is that there is further work necessary to elaborate in specific details on how project activities and outputs complement each other - in terms of overlaps, synergies, and differences or gaps. The Network Map serves as a basis to guide specific project interactions. This can be done through direct interaction and discussion between participating partners or evaluation of project proposals to identify connections across tasks, and WPs (as illustrated in Section 2.1). However, a less biased manner is to continue using an AI-LM based approach (ChatGPT), and in this was applied to data extracted from the respective Grant Agreements of the sister projects to legumES, i.e., VALERECO, and LEGENDARY. This metadata included WP activities/descriptions, and Deliverable titles.

The narrative below provides a full synthesis comparing the three Horizon-funded projects legumES, LEGENDARY and VALERECO, including a unified ecosystem services (ESs) framework, project overlaps, complementarities, differences, and gaps relative to the EC Horizon Europe call topic, ‘HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-16’; noting that all terminology has been normalised across projects. Since, normalising terms helps effective communication and collaboration, and while a common projects’ glossary has not been generated, the terms chosen should be readily recognised.

The findings from across all three projects will advance our understanding, quantification, and governance capacities of/for the ESs provided by legumes and legume-based systems, and products.

5.1. A Unified ESs Framework

To harmonise analysis across the three projects, ES categories were normalised into a unified framework which comprised the following 12 ES domains – listed below after Figure 15, which illustrates ESs of strong and low overlap.

Figure 15. A heatmap of ecosystem service coverage (alignment; 0-3) across the three projects LEGENDARY VELERECO, and legumES with complete alignment (3) shown in yellow, and no alignment (0) in black.

Figure 15 heatmap above highlights the generally very strong alignment across the three projects LEGENDARY VELERECO, and legumES, though key areas of difference or complementarity are also found.

The 12 distinct ES domains identified across the three projects are defined in more specific detail below.

1. **N-related services:** biological nitrogen fixation (BNF), N cycling, reduced synthetic N, N transfer, reduced N losses.
2. **Soil health & carbon:** soil structure, carbon, fertility, erosion control.
3. **Biodiversity:** above- and below-ground biodiversity including pollinators, natural enemies, flora, soil microbiota.
4. **Climate regulation:** greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation, emissions impacts, climate adaptation.
5. **Water regulation & quality:** water use, runoff, infiltration, erosion via water, water quality.
6. **Yield & yield stability:** yield levels, inter-annual stability, quality traits.
7. **Weed, pest & disease regulation:** weed suppression, pest and disease pressures, reduced pesticide applications.
8. **Semi-natural & landscape ES:** Legumes in semi-natural habitats, landscape-level functions.
9. **Socio-economic services:** farm income, risk, labour, regional economic impacts.
10. **Cultural & dietary services:** diet quality, cultural values, aesthetic landscape benefits.
11. **Governance & policy:** CAP & policy levers, ES-based incentives, governance analyses.
12. **Tools, indicators & DSSs (Decision Support Systems):** indicator sets, data platforms, advisory decision-support tools.

The similarities and differences above are also illustrated below in a radial diagram, (Figure 16).

Figure 16. ES coverage (0 = none, 3 = strong) radial chart across the three projects show that, with the green, blue, and yellow lines representing LEGENDARY, VALERECO, and legumES (respectively).

In addition, and from deeper elaboration, we can elaborate the following.

- All three projects strongly address N services, climate, yield, pest/disease, socio-economic dimensions, policy, and decision support.
- LEGENDARY has more activity on sensor-based quantification and cultural/lifestyle ESs.
- VALERECO encompasses more activity on behavioural economics, market analysis, consumer behaviour, and integrated DSS/hub infrastructure.
- legumES is strongest on semi-natural systems (even with only a limited number of non-crop legume-based Pilot Studies), landscape ES, policy modelling, and integration of ES into LCA.

5.2. WP-Level Thematic Mapping

A cross-project harmonised mapping of WPs reveals nine thematic ‘activity domains’ (excluding coordination), as follows.

- 1. Stakeholder engagement & multi-actor processes**
 - a. LEGENDARY: Workshops, focus groups, broad agronomic sector engagement.
 - b. VALERECO: Behavioural WP with farmers, retailers, consumers; Living Lab co-creation.
 - c. legumES: Strong co-creation (Innovation Camps, actor engagement).
- 2. Living labs, Pilot Studies & on-farm trials**
 - a. LEGENDARY: Multi-site, multi-annual trials of annual and perennial legumes.
 - b. VALERECO: On-station trials and Living Labs across 6 EU countries.
 - c. legumES: 25 Pilot Studies including of semi-natural systems’, with some seeking to develop as Living Labs; also, (supported) participatory farmer involvement.
- 3. ES data & indicator development**
 - a. LEGENDARY: Sensor-based ES metrics and ES benchmarks.
 - b. VALERECO: ES catalogue, statistical modelling, DSS algorithms.
 - c. legumES: ES indicators, and DSSs ‘ES Navigator’, ‘DiCES’.
- 4. Environmental assessment & LCA**
 - a. LEGENDARY: ES-informed LCA for sustainability assessments.
 - b. VALERECO: Living Lab-level LCA with comparison to imports.
 - c. legumES: has a greater focus on activities which seek to integrate ESs into LCA (attributional- & consequential-LCA).
- 5. Economic assessment & adoption**
 - a. LEGENDARY: Farm-scale ES valuation and socio-economic analysis.
 - b. VALERECO: Behavioural economics, consumer studies, Living Lab CBA (cost benefit analysis)/LCA.
 - c. legumES: market modelling, adoption ABMs (agent-based models), socio-economic impact.
- 6. Policy, governance & CAP**
 - a. LEGENDARY: practical policy guidance and socio-economic recommendations.

- b. VALERECO: CAP analysis, policy briefs linked to Living Lab evidence.
- c. legumES: detailed policy scanning, e-Delphi, governance modelling.

7. Digital tools & DSS

- a. LEGENDARY: sensor-driven model toolbox and web-based DSS.
- b. VALERECO: DSS + 'Digital Legume Information Hub' with database & API.
- c. legumES: AgriToolkit, ES Navigator, DiCES, ADIES.

8. Capacity building & dissemination

- a. LEGENDARY: National/international conferences, practice abstract.
- b. VALERECO: Structured training, capacity-building, DEC plan.
- c. legumES: educational materials, training and cocreation workshops, plus Innovation Camps.

5.3. Deliverable Clusters (Overlaps and Differences)

Deliverables were grouped into seven cross-project clusters, identified as follows.

1. **ES datasets & experimental data:** all projects create extensive ES datasets.
 - a. LEGENDARY adds sensor/UAV remote-sensing ES data.
 - b. VALERECO focuses Living Lab/on-station datasets.
 - c. legumES emphasises diverse pilot studies including semi-natural systems.
2. **ES indicator methods & monitoring protocols**
 - a. Common across all three, though greatest activity in developing new or novel methodologies appears greater in legumES and LEGENDARY.
 - b. VALERECO focusses on integrating indicators into DSS.
3. **Environmental assessment & LCA outputs**
 - a. legumES: ES-integrated LCAs.
 - b. LEGENDARY: ES-LCA within sustainability assessment.
 - c. VALERECO: Living Lab-based LCA and import comparisons.
4. **Economic analysis & CBA**
 - a. legumES: Global & EU legume pathways, adoption simulation.
 - b. LEGENDARY: ES valuation + cost-benefit.
 - c. VALERECO: Behavioural work + Living Lab-level CBA extrapolated to national scales.
5. **Policy outputs**
 - a. legumES: Strong modelling + governance tools.
 - b. LEGENDARY: Policy guidance from ES benchmarks.
 - c. VALERECO: CAP-specific policy briefs tied to Living Lab findings.
6. **Digital tools & DSS**
 - a. legumES: Full suite of advisory & policy DSS tools.
 - b. LEGENDARY: ES model toolbox and web-DSS.
 - c. VALERECO: DSS + Digital Hub.

7. Capacity building & dissemination

- a. All contribute: LEGENDARY & VALERECO strongest on outreach volume; legumES strong on educational/ES framing resources.

5.4. Designing a seminar series to add cross-project value

Building on these synergies, complementarities, and gaps identified between **legumES**, **VALERECO**, and **LEGENDARY**, a future **seminar series** (or international meeting/conference) is conceived only as a suggestion at this stage - as a proposed structured journey to be developed further and agreed with partners of the sister projects.

Whatever final structure the final plan for the webinar series (or conference), takes, s should aim to mirror the progression and insights emerging from the cross-project comparison. The series begins by establishing shared conceptual ground, moves through methodological harmonisation, supports digital and data integration, and culminates in coordinated policy and societal engagement. In doing so, it functions not only as a forum for knowledge exchange but as a **deliberate mechanism for closing the strategic, methodological, and operational gaps**.

The first set of seminars could focus on building a common foundation across projects. While all three initiatives contribute to a shared constellation of twelve ES domains, each project brings a distinct emphasis. The opening seminar will therefore centre on forming a **Unified ES Framework**, establishing common terminology and shared definitions needed for coherent collaboration. This may be followed by a seminar mapping WP activity across the projects for areas of deep alignment and strategic complementarity. A third seminar could examine the seven deliverable clusters, enabling partners to understand where outputs reinforce each other and where coordinated effort is essential to avoid duplication or address missing capacities.

With this common understanding established, the series would then transition into a block dedicated to **methodological harmonisation**, responding directly to gaps in ES indicators, monitoring protocols, LCA integration, and economic modelling. A seminar on ES indicator alignment brings together LEGENDARY's sensor-driven metrics, VALERECO's DSS-integrated indicators, and legumES' ES-LCA frameworks to develop a shared minimum indicator set and common monitoring principles. Another seminar addresses the lack of harmonised ES-LCA methods across projects, using legumES' more advanced modelling as a basis for constructing a **joint ES-LCA protocol**. A further session unites VALERECO's behavioural insights, LEGENDARY's ES valuation, and legumES' agent-based adoption modelling to resolve the currently fragmented economic analysis landscape and create a **unified 'ecosystem-service-responsive adoption model'**.

The third block of the series would do well to focus on **digital tools and data governance**, as significant fragmentation is highlighted here: each project develops valuable DSSs and digital platforms, but there is no shared architecture, no agreement on interoperability, and no common data governance strategy. A dedicated seminar brings together the developers of the various DSSs -ADIES, ES Navigator, DiCES, the VALERECO Hub, and the LEGENDARY DSS - to identify opportunities for shared modules, federated structures, or API-based integration. A complementary seminar responds to the absence of a joint data strategy by establishing shared metadata standards, governance protocols, and FAIR data principles to support cross-project synthesis and long-term accessibility.

The final block in the series could move outward, addressing the **societal, governance, and policy gaps** that have been identified. Although each project generates policy-relevant outputs, they do so with

differing emphases: legumES produces advanced governance models, VALERECO brings CAP-level policy insights, and LEGENDARY offers ES-based recommendations. A seminar in this block therefore focuses on developing **coordinated policy messages** and a **shared Missions Document**, ensuring that joint findings are communicated with coherence and strategic alignment. The concluding seminar tackles another area of complementarity and under-addressed opportunity: the connection between legumes, cultural ecosystem services, dietary patterns, and citizen engagement. By combining LEGENDARY’s cultural ES work, VALERECO’s consumer analyses, and legumES broader ES framing, the seminar creates the foundation for a **citizen- and culture-oriented communication toolkit** that expands the reach of project outcomes beyond technical audiences.

Across all these stages, this initial proposal for a seminar series is intentionally structured to not only foster collaboration but to **systematically address the methodological, conceptual, and strategic gaps identified through the Section 4 comparative analysis**. By aligning ES frameworks, harmonising indicators and assessment tools, integrating digital infrastructures, and unifying policy and societal engagement efforts, the series transforms areas of divergence into opportunities for collective advancement. In doing so, it strengthens the combined scientific, technical, and societal impact of the three projects, positioning their joint work as a coherent and powerful contribution to the European transition toward resilient, legume-supported agroecosystems.

To summarise, a consolidated list of the key outputs generated across the entire seminar series, or explicitly stated in the integrated narrative, would be as follows.

1. **Unified Ecosystem Services (ES) Lexicon & Coding Framework:** a shared terminology across the 12 ES domains to help enable consistent communication and cross-project synthesis.
2. **Cross-Project WP Alignment Matrix:** mapped WP activities correspond across legumES, VALERECO, and LEGENDARY, highlighting synergies and opportunities for joint work.
3. **Cross-Project Deliverable Atlas:** consolidated view of major deliverables across all three projects, identifying overlaps, complementarities, and missing elements.
4. **Harmonised ES Indicator Set:** an agreed suite of ES indicators, drawing from sensor-based metrics, DSS-linked indicators, and ES–LCA measures.
6. **Joint legume ES–LCA Protocol:** a common methodological framework for integrating ESs into LCA, enabling comparable sustainability evaluations across projects.
7. **Unified ESR (Ecosystem-Service-Responsive) Adoption Model:** a combined framework incorporating behavioural economics, ES valuation, and farm-level adoption modelling to support more robust socio-economic insights.
8. **DSS Interoperability Blueprint:** a conceptual and technical framework describing how ADIES, ES Navigator, DiCES, VALERECO Hub, and LEGENDARY’s DSS can interoperate or share modules.
9. **Cross-Project FAIR Data Charter:** a shared data-governance principles, metadata standards, and protocols to enable integrated datasets and long-term accessibility.
10. **Cross-Project Policy Missions Document:** coordinated policy messages and strategic recommendations for EU, national, and regional governance bodies to support legume-based ES.
11. **Citizen & Cultural ES Communication Toolkit:** shared outreach resources connecting legumes to cultural, dietary, and landscape benefits to support societal engagement.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Summary

The objective of D7.4 was to create a Network Map to visualise EU funded projects complementary to legumES as a means by which greater awareness may be achieved of projects funded historically, and so their outputs. In addition, for still live projects the opportunity to connect with complementary projects with a view to support future joint activity development and cross-project collaboration.

A data framework has been developed and described based on data gathered from CORDIS whereby EU funded projects relating to legumes which are captured in a database (first in Excel™, and the Google Sheet) which can be exploited using Kumu. The [EU Projects database](#) is Open Access and may be exploited using filtering and data visualisation tools for used by stakeholders - to create their own unique database of projects or add to the online legumES [Google Sheet](#) database and [Kumu](#) hosted Network Map.

This 'living' [Network Map](#) can facilitate cross-initiative and cross-project collaboration by showcasing both active and closed projects, along with overviews of their scope.

Furthermore, and as illustrated for the live sister projects (legumES, VALERECO, and LEGENDARY), the mapping approach can be bolstered by gathering of additional metadata (here Deliverable titles and WP activity descriptions) to identify focal areas for synergistic collaborations, such as informing the design of seminars, workshop as a basis for collaboration and future research.

5.2. Next steps

In addition to supporting collaboration among active projects, the Network Map can be significantly strengthened by integrating metadata, for example as are available from completed archived project deliverables, incorporating deliverable titles, summaries, methodological outputs, and tools from historic EU-funded initiatives. The plan would then be to design a reliable system for evaluating project outputs in a specialised domain, and to begin by leveraging a LLM to define and extract expert-level evaluation criteria, create detailed rubrics, outline decision rules, and generate examples of high-quality assessments. With this framework in place, a SLM (small language model), which shows greater efficacy in domain specific arenas (here for 'legumes') can be used for 'instruction training'; while later use of LLM (large language model) -generated rubric, along with real domain examples (metadata) of previous project outputs, may be used of data mining and synthesis. The SLM would learn to apply the criteria consistently, quickly, and privately - using local infrastructure and maintain predictable scoring behaviour; this would be allied to the insight generating potential of the LLM. At this stage, there is no database

This approach would transform the map into a comprehensive, searchable knowledge database. Such an enriched resource would not only prevent duplication and enable systematic synthesis of past work and provide the European Commission (and other funders) with clear evidence of where research saturation has been reached and where genuine gaps persist. This, in turn, can guide the design of better targeted, more strategic future funding calls.

Likewise, policymakers would gain clearer insight into which interventions have already been tested, which are most likely to demonstrate impact. Where further action is required, this is allowing for more effective, evidence-based policy development across agri-food, biodiversity, and ecosystem-

services domains. In this way, the **legumES Network Map** would evolve into a powerful instrument for cumulative learning and strategic decision-making within both research and policy spheres.

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